

Charles Darwin *In Memoriam*

Evolutionary looks at the why of biological and cultural phenomena.

A new, non-mutualistic hypothesis for why sloths defecate on the ground

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ABSTRACT: Sloth are arboreal mammals that descend to defecate and urinate on the ground, increasing the risk of predation by ground animals, perhaps to leave chemical messages for other sloths or to fertilize the tree. A more recent hypothesis postulates a mutualistic model: sloths feed on the algae that grow in their fur, and the algae in turn are fertilized by dead moths. The moth larvae develop on the feces and are somehow benefited if the fecal pellets are not simply dropped from the canopy. This model was applied to *Bradypus variegatus*, which has more moths, algae and nitrogen in its skin than a sloth that sometimes defecates from the canopy, *Choloepus hoffmanni*. There is currently no qualitative or quantitative evidence that the moths benefit from feces deposited on the ground, or that they benefit the algae in any way, but the hypothesis could still be correct if it were not for one reason: sloths do not lick hair to consume the algae, and it is unlikely that they feed through their skin. The algal traces found in their stomachs could originate in epiphyllous algae that grow on the leaves they eat, and the tests with cow inoculum are probably misleading: the mutualism hypothesis has problems that should be considered before accepting it at face value. The new hypothesis, which fits all known data, is that the answer may be simpler, not only *B. variegatus*, but all six species of sloths defecate on the ground because they have always defecated on the ground, and predation has not been strong enough to select against it. This article includes a list of experiments and field observations to give a more robust answer to the question of why sloths descend to the ground to defecate.

KEY WORDS: evolution of sloth behavior, natural selection on defecation, mutualism, moths, *Bradypus spp.*, *Choloepus spp.*, algae, feces, arboreal mammals.

Sloths are arboreal mammals that harbor a complex community of organisms in their fur, including moths and algae (Aiello, 1985; Vaughan, Ramírez, Herrera, & Guries 2007; Ramirez, Vaughan, Herrera, & Guries, 2011). Sloth descend to defecate and urinate on the ground,

increasing the risk of predation by ground animals, perhaps to leave chemical messages for other sloths; to fertilize the tree; or to increase fur moth populations (Pauli et al., 2014).

The moth mutualism hypothesis postulates that instead of dropping feces from the tree, sloths deposit them on the ground to increase algal populations in their own fur. The sloth *Bradypus variegatus* always defecates on the ground and covers its feces, in what can be called a shallow latrine; in these visits to the latrine, the moths fly to the dung and oviposit, the larvae feed and pupate in the dung, and the new generation of moths fly to the canopy in search of a sloth to mate and feed (possibly on organically rich liquids from the sloth hair and skin). Finally, the moths die inside the fur and their decomposed bodies fertilize the layer of algae that the sloth licks to improve its diet (Pauli et al., 2014); optionally, the algal nutrients might somehow be absorbed through the skin (Aiello, 1985).

According to Pauli et al. (2014), sloths suffer significant predation when they descend to defecate, so the benefits of the mutualistic relationship with the moths must be significant. This model is supported by data: Pauli et al. (2014) showed that the latrine species, *Bradypus variegatus*, (1) has more moths, algae and nitrogen in its skin than *Choloepus hoffmanni*, a sloth that sometimes defecates from the canopy; (2) that it has the same type of algae in its fur and its digestive system and (3) that these calory-rich algae can be digested by compounds from cow stomachs.

However, this mutualism hypothesis has serious problems, which I analyze here in detail:

***Bradypus variegatus* feeds exclusively on leaves**

A more recent study reports that *B. variegatus* also feeds on fruit (Carita, 2019), so it is probably not as dependent on an exclusive low-nutrient leaf diet as stated by Pauli et al. (2014). Opposite to expectation, this “nutritionally-stressed” species needs smaller home ranges than the supposedly less nutritionally stressed *C. hoffmanni*, which, by the way, is cited by several authors (Hayssen, 2011) as feeding on animal matter, but Dünner and Pastor (2017) report that they have never found animal remains in autopsies or stomach contents.

It always defecates on the ground and covers its feces

This statement is in agreement with current knowledge (Dünner & Pastor, 2017).

Moth development in the dung is favored by the latrine

There are no data to support this statement, but sloth dung consists of relatively dry pellets that would probably stay available even if dropped from the canopy (Dünner & Pastor, 2017). IN favor of the mutualistic hypothesis, I can find three factors: finding the pellets to lay their eggs would be more difficult for the moths; they might be exposed to predation during the search; and, additionally, uncovered pellets might last less time as a fit microhabitat for the larvae and pupae. We just do not have any data about these three factors.

The moths feed on organically rich liquids from the sloth hair and skin

There are no data to support this statement, but it is a reasonable assumption, ripe for direct study.

The moths die inside the fur

There are no data to support this statement, I personally have not seen dead moths in the fur of sloths, but this would also be easy to study.

The decomposed bodies of the moths fertilize the layer of algae

There are no data to support this statement, but it is appropriate for experimental study.

The sloth licks the algae from its hair to improve its diet

Bradypus variegatus and other sloths do not lick themselves, or each other (Aiello, 1985), the only exception seems to be *Choloepus didactylus* (Adam, 1999) and, in any case, the algae grow mostly outside the reach of the short and relatively dry tongues of sloths (Dünner & Pastor, 2017).

The nutrients might be somehow absorbed through the skin

It is unlikely that useful amounts of nutrients can be absorbed through the skin of mammals (e.g. Semple, 2004), but there are no studies for sloths. This would be more difficult to study.

The spongy sloth hairs evolved to favor the growth of algae

The spongy sloth hairs are unique in the animal world and seem adapted to the benefit of the algae (Aiello, 1985); however, spongy hair may also have been favored by natural selection for other reasons, like keeping beneficial bacteria (Chen, Fischbach, & Belkaid, 2018), as protection from thermic extremes, or to keep the skin itself dry in the rainforest (the spongy hairs absorb moisture and keep it in the outer hair layer). Once such spongy hair evolved, algae and many other organisms could easily exploit the new niche, and DNA work shows that the biota on sloth hair is far more varied and complex than previously thought, with frequent misidentification of the algae (Suutari et al., 2010; Kaup, 2020).

Sloths suffer significant predation when they descend to defecate

The hypothesis states that *B. variegatus* descends to the ground but pays a high cost in predation, while *C. hoffmanni* defecates from the relative safety of branches and is less affected by predation (Pauli et al., 2014), but a study in Costa Rica found the opposite: observers counted 5.5 times less cases of predation of *B. variegatus* than of *C. hoffmanni* (Table 2 in Peery & Pauli, 2014). However, in fairness, it must be said that documenting natural predation rates on sloths is difficult; the available data are from opportunistic observations and from animals marked with radio devices in areas close to human activity, which hardly reflect the predatory pressure under which sloths evolved in the past.

Stomach algae prove that the animal licks algae from its hair

The study by Pauli et al. (2014) did not check if the same algae grow on the leaves that the sloths eat. The algae may also occur in their surrounding habitat (Suutari et al., 2010) and this could

explain why some were found in the stomachs. In fact, Pauli et al. (2014) found that 83 % of *B. variegatus* digesta samples did *not* have any algal remains, but explained this absence as the result of rapid digestion.

The test with cow ruminal inoculum shows that sloths digest algae

According to Dünner and Pastor (2017) this assumption is not valid because the digestive capacities of cows and sloths are completely different.

Other ideas about sloths, algae and moths

In any case, it must also be mentioned that, with the exception of *Bradypus pygmaeus*, for which I could not find any mention of whether it lost the moths when it swam to the Panamanian island where it currently lives, the other species of *Bradypus* (*B. pygmaeus*, *B. torquatus* and *B. tridactylus*) have similar natural histories, with the same moths and algae, but we do not know if they build latrines (Lara-Ruiz & Chiarello, 2005; Hayssen, 2009; Kaviar, Shockey, & Sundberg, 2012). *B. tridactylus* leaves uncovered piles of pellets on the ground if the weather is dry, but drops them from the tree if it is raining (Hayssen, 2009).

There are other possible reasons why *B. variegatus* benefits from defecating on the ground, the ones mentioned before and that have not been experimentally studied yet: that it concentrates the fecal nutrients as fertilizer in the base of the trees where they feed; and that the latrines preserve chemical territorial or mating messages for other sloths.

All ideas until now have been based on one assumption: the behavior of ground defecation has evolved because its benefit is greater than the cost of predation. Here I present a new hypothesis, not based on that assumption.

New hypothesis

The new hypothesis that I propose here is that *sloths defecate on the ground because there maintain their ancestral defecation behavior and there has been no selective pressure for them to defecate from the canopy*. The six extant species of sloths are the only surviving descendants of a much larger group of terrestrial mammals (Slater et al., 2016) whose size and body structure indicates that they defecated on the ground, and, I add, probably covered their feces to avoid attracting predators and parasites, like many mammals do.

Supporting references for the new hypothesis

Defecation from the canopy in species with less moths seems to have been overstated, I cannot find any papers quantifying this: the literature suggests that all species defecate on the ground (Sunquist & Montgomery, 1973; Waage & Best, 1985; Hayssen, 2009, Hayssen, 2011; Slater et al., 2016; Dünner & Pastor, 2017), independently of how many moths and algae they harbor. At most, we know that *B. tridactylus* sometimes defecates from the canopy and sometimes on the ground, but no longer covers the feces (Waage & Best, 1985; Hayssen, 2009), and the two species of *Choloepus*, an evolutionarily more derived group (Slater et al., 2016) also defecate on the ground (Sunquist, & Montgomery, 1973; Hayssen, 2011).

In conclusion, the mutualism hypothesis has many problems that should be considered before accepting it at face value: there is still much work to do before we put to rest the question of why sloths descend to defecate, the answer may be far simpler, not only *B. variegatus*, but all six species of sloths do it because they have always defecated on the ground, and predation is not strong enough to select against it.

REFERENCES

- Adam, P. (1999). *Choloepus didactylus*. *Mammalian Species*, 621, 1-8. doi: 10.2307/3504332
- Aiello, A. (1985). Sloth hair: unanswered questions. In G. G. Montgomery(ed). *The Evolution of Armadillos, Sloths, and Vermilinguas* (pp. 213-218). Washington, D.C., USA: Smithsonian Institution Press.
- Carita, T. T. (2019). *Etología de Bradypus variegatus (perezoso de tres dedos) en la Isla de la Tipishca del río Samiria, en temporada de vaciante, Reserva Nacional Pacaya -Samiria, Loreto -Perú, 2016* (Thesis). Biología, Universidad Nacional Jorge Basadre Grohmann, Tacna, Perú.
- Chen, Y. E., Fischbach, M. A., & Belkaid, Y. (2018). Skin microbiota–host interactions. *Nature*, 553(7689), 427-436. doi: 10.1038/nature25177
- Dünner, C. & Pastor, G. (2017). *Manual de manejo, medicina y rehabilitación de perezosos*. Chile: Fundación Huálamo.
- Hayssen, V. (2009). *Bradypus tridactylus* (Pilosa: Bradypodidae). *Mammalian Species*, 839, 1-9. doi: 10.1644/839.1
- Hayssen, V. (2011). *Choloepus hoffmanni* (Pilosa: Megalonychidae). *Mammalian Species*, 43(873), 37-55. doi: 10.1644/873.1
- Kaup, M. (2020). *Elucidating the Sloth Hair Microbiome: A Metagenomic Comparison Of Two- And Three-Fingered Sloths* (M.Sc.Thesis). University of Mississippi, USA. Retrieved from <https://egrove.olemiss.edu/etd/1880>
- Kaviar, S., Shockey, J., & Sundberg, P. (2012). Observations on the endemic pygmy three-toed sloth, *Bradypus pygmaeus* of Isla Escudo de Veraguas, Panama. *PloS one*, 7(11), e49854. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0049854
- Lara-Ruiz, P., & Chiarello, A. G. (2005). Life-history traits and sexual dimorphism of the Atlantic forest maned sloth *Bradypus torquatus* (Xenarthra: Bradypodidae). *Journal of Zoology*, 267(1), 63-73. doi: 10.1017/S0952836905007259

- Peery, M. Z., & Pauli, J. N. (2014). Shade-grown cacao supports a self-sustaining population of two-toed but not three-toed sloths. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, *51*(1), 162-170. doi: 10.1111/1365-2664.12182
- Pauli, J. N., Mendoza, J. E., Steffan, S. A., Carey, C. C., Weimer, P. J., & Peery, M. Z. (2014). A syndrome of mutualism reinforces the lifestyle of a sloth. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *281*(1778), 20133006. doi: 10.1098/rspb.2013.3006
- Ramirez, O., Vaughan, C., Herrera, G., & Guries, R. (2011). Temporal and spatial resource use by female three-toed sloths and their young in an agricultural landscape in Costa Rica. *Revista de Biología Tropical*, *59*(4), 1743-1755.
- Semple, S. (2004). Dermal exposure to chemicals in the workplace: just how important is skin absorption?. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, *61*(4), 376-382. doi: 10.1136/oem.2003.010645
- Slater, G. J., Cui, P., Forasiepi, A. M., Lenz, D., Tsangaras, K., Voirin, B., ... & Greenwood, A. D. (2016). Evolutionary relationships among extinct and extant sloths: the evidence of mitogenomes and retroviruses. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, *8*(3), 607-621. doi: 10.1093/gbe/evw023
- Sunquist, M. E., & Montgomery, G. G. (1973). Activity patterns and rates of movement of two-toed and three-toed sloths (*Choloepus hoffmanni* and *Bradypus infuscatus*). *Journal of Mammalogy*, *54*(4), 946-954. doi: 10.2307/1379088
- Suutari, M., Majaneva, M., Fewer, D. P., Voirin, B., Aiello, A., Friedl, T., ... & Blomster, J. (2010). Molecular evidence for a diverse green algal community growing in the hair of sloths and a specific association with *Trichophilus welckeri* (Chlorophyta, Ulvophyceae). *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, *10*(1), 1-12. doi: 10.1186/1471-2148-10-86
- Vaughan, C., Ramírez, O., Herrera, G., & Guries, R. (2007). Spatial ecology and conservation of two sloth species in a cacao landscape in Limón, Costa Rica. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, *16*(8), 2293-2310. doi: 10.1007/s10531-007-9191-5
- Waage, J. K., & Best, C. (1985). Arthropod associates of sloths. In G. G. Montgomery (ed). *The Evolution of Armadillos, Sloths, and Vermilinguas* (pp. 297-311). Washington, D.C., USA: Smithsonian Institution Press.
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